

Surgical Outcome of the Lateral Impaction Shoulder Injury: A Rare Case Report

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Abstract:

This case report presents the clinical course and management of lateral impaction shoulder injury in a tertiary hospital setting. A then 42-year-old male presented with left shoulder deformity with global restriction of movements at the affected shoulder joint. Detailed examination revealed dropping of left shoulder with minimum ROM at the joint. Diagnostic workup confirmed fracture of medial end of ipsilateral clavicle with ipsilateral scapula fracture with ipsilateral ribs fracture, and treatment consisted of open reduction and plating for clavicle and scapula keeping in consideration of shoulder suspensory ligament complex. Follow-up assessments after 6 months demonstrated correction in drooping of shoulder and complete functional ROM. This report highlights fractures associated with lateral impaction of shoulder and discusses relevant literature to underscore the management challenges and outcomes associated with it.

Keywords: SSSC, Medial Clavicle, Ipsilateral Ribs, Lateral Impaction of Shoulder.

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Introduction

The shoulder joint forms a functional unit of the upper extremity which provides a stable biomechanical construct to allow efficient transfer of force from the hand to the axial spine [1]. Trauma to the lateral aspect of the shoulder is common. The force is generally mild which leads to the fracture of the clavicle, but severe high-energy trauma is rare [2]. The lateral impaction of the shoulder is a rare trauma that corresponds to the transmission of the force applied by the humerus on the scapula [3].

The medial end of the clavicle fracture is rare and makes up about 5% of the total clavicular fractures [4]. In a large majority of cases, fractures of the medial end of the clavicle are associated with visceral injuries [5].

Scarlat et al studied the force vector and biomechanics in the lateral impaction injury to the shoulder [2]. They mentioned that the force is divided into two vectors namely anterosuperior and posteroinferior direction. They described the shoulder complex to be made up of two arches, anterior and posterior. The anterior arch is composed of the acromio-clavicular joint, sternoclavicular joint, costo-calvicular joint. While the posterior arch is composed of the glenohumeral joint, scapula, and scapulothoracic joint. The two arches are connected by the superior suspensory ligament complex [2].

The concept of the superior shoulder suspensory complex which comprises the bone and soft tissue rings secured to the trunk by the superior and inferior bony struts was first described in 1993 [6].

Scarlat et al also described internal and external lesions associated with the lateral impaction injury to the shoulder. The external lesions include superficial injury to the shoulder girdle, humeral head, glenohumeral fracture, and soft tissue trauma. While the internal lesions comprised the ribs and thoracic injuries, mediastinal injuries, and neurovascular injuries [2]. They were also able to attribute both simple and complex lesions of the shoulder injuries to the lateral impaction mechanism. They termed the internal as well as the external lesions encountered during the injury to be co-existent lesions [2].

Poggetti et al also described a similar injury mechanism to the lateral aspect of the shoulder joint with the progression of the vector steering posteriorly resulting in the involvement of the acromion, glenoid, and scapular neck. High-energy injury can disrupt both anterior and posterior arches and usually cause internal lesions [7]. Ouede et al also described that the fracture of the clavicle and the ribs occur similarly as the high-energy trauma for scapula fractures [8].

The proximity of the tissue to the side of the injury absorbs the impact and results in severe lesions of the skin, subcutaneous tissue, and deltoid muscles. There can be associated injury to ribs, brachial plexus, or pneumothorax. Scapular fractures have been associated with ribs and clavicular fractures, pleuro-pulmonary lesions, extremity fractures, and cervical spine trauma [2]. The sternoclavicular joint is the most stable joint and resistant joint in the locomotor system. LA fosse et al reported a variant of lateral Impaction injury with postero-lateral dislocation of the sternoclavicular joint [5].

Case Presentation

Patient Information: A 42-year-old male with right-hand dominance had come to the emergency department with a history of road traffic accidents

with injury to the shoulder and chest. The patient had drooping of the Left shoulder with difficulty in breathing. The patient was managed at a local hospital at first and was then later referred to our hospital.

Clinical Findings: On Examination, the patient had drooping of the left shoulder, there was a contusion over the clavicular and the scapular region. The shoulder was displaced medially as compared to the opposite side [Figure 1].

There was no moment at the shoulder joint. All the distal neurological functions were intact.

Other general investigations of the patient were done and were found to be within normal limits.

Figure 1: Clinical image of the patient with drooping of Left shoulder with contusion over the clavicular region

Timeline: The patient presented with an injury to the shoulder joint with drooping of the left shoulder and difficulty in breathing. The patient had trauma due to a road traffic accident which was initially managed conservatively at a local hospital and presented 2 days later. The patient had undergone investigations such as an X-ray of the shoulder joint with clavicle and an X-ray of the chest. A CT scan of the shoulder joint with a CT scan of the thorax and scapula was also done to better delineate the fracture anatomy. Meticulous planning was done while the patient was being stabilized and surgery was performed. The patient at 6 months follow-up had a complete functional range of motion at the shoulder joint with overhead abduction of more than 140 degrees, internal and external rotation at the shoulder of 30 and 50 degrees respectively, and forward flexion effortlessly with continuation above

the shoulder level. The patient was able to get back to his daily living

Diagnostic Assessment and Interpretation: For diagnosis of the fracture, an anteroposterior x-ray of the shoulder joint with clavicle was obtained. The x-ray showed a fracture of the scapular neck region with a fracture of the medial edge of the scapula. There was a fracture of the clavicle at the medial end with multiple rib fractures. The medial end of the clavicle was displaced superiorly, with comminution at the fracture site [Figure 2]. There was a severe depression of the shoulder with comminution at the scapula.

A radiograph of the chest anteroposterior view showed multiple fractures of the ribs at the 3rd, 4th, and 5th levels. A CT scan was also obtained for all the fractures to delineate the fracture anatomy and to understand the fracture better [Figure 3,4,5].

Figure 2: x-ray showing fracture of the medial end of the clavicle with fracture of the scapula (A) - AP view (B) - shoulder abducted and externally rotated

Figure 3: 3-D reconstruction showing ipsilateral multiple ribs fracture with scapula fracture posterior view

Figure 4: 3-D reconstruction showing ipsilateral multiple ribs fracture and scapula fracture (lateral)

Figure 5: 3-D reconstruction showing ipsilateral multiple ribs fracture, with medial end clavicle and scapula fracture (AP view)

Intervention

The primary plan was to fix the clavicle fracture as well as the scapular fracture, to restore the height of the shoulder as well as medial displacement. The chest tube was placed in situ till after the surgery. The scapular fracture was addressed first, with the patient in a lateral position with the injured site up. A curved incision [figure 6] was taken along the

spinous process and fracture was managed with a 3.5mm recon plate along the medial border of the scapula and the spinous process, while another plate was used to fix the lateral border of the scapula [Figure 7,8,9].

Clavicle fracture was addressed later. Clavicle fracture was managed with plate osteosynthesis in supine position.

Figure 6: Image showing the curved incision over the scapula

Figure 7: Image showing the dissection done after incision

Figure 8: image showing the fixation of the scapular fracture with reconstruction plate

Figure 9: Immediate postoperative x-ray (Antero -Posterior views)

Follow-up and Outcome

The patient was discharged on post-operative day 14, after assessing the wound and suture removal. As the patient presented with a drooping shoulder and restricted range of movements around the left shoulder joint, on 1 month follow up the patient was pain-free, the deformity of the drooping of the shoulder was corrected along with an improved

range of motion around 40 degrees abduction, 90-degrees forward flexion and 20 degrees internal and 30-degrees external rotation.

The patient showed great compliance with regular follow-ups and vigorous and sincere physiotherapy which showed promising results at 6 months follow-up with almost complete functional range of motion around the shoulder joint [figure 10-14]

Figure 10: Flexion of the shoulder on 6- month follow-up

Figure 11: Extension of the shoulder on 6-month follow-up

Figure 12: Internal rotation of the shoulder joint on 6- month follow-up

Figure 13: External rotation of the shoulder joint on 6-month follow-up

Figure 14: Clinical image showing the restoration of the shoulder height

Discussion

Lateral impaction scapular fractures are quite uncommon injuries. Trauma to the shoulder suspensory ligament complex is also usually correlated with lateral impaction injuries [2]. The 2 struts suspend the proximal girdle, namely the superior strut formed by the clavicular middle part and the inferior strut formed by the scapular body lateral part and spine of the scapula [9]. A direct sideways impact on the acromion when the shoulder is positioned in adduction creates a compressive force that pushes the acromion downward and forward compared to the clavicle, influenced by the joint's inherent angle [10]. Non-operative treatment is less recommended due to the risk of weakness in abduction weakness, reduced range of motion, and mal-union and non-union with pain which is chronic in nature. Sheenan stated that primary repair of the fracture in younger patients with high functional demands is beneficial [10].

In the mentioned case, our patient had an injury to the shoulder joint with a chest injury. The purpose of taking over this challenging surgery was to bring back shoulder function to a level where the patient can carry on with his daily activities without aid and to correct the deformity caused by the patient's overlook of the nature of the fracture.

As supported by the 6-month follow-up range of motion, both the function and cosmetic aspects of the fracture were taken care of. Scarlet et al mentioned research on 17 subjects with lateral impaction injury of the shoulder. They insisted on looking for internal and external lesions in cases where both the arches of the shoulder girdle are disrupted. They encountered rib fractures as the most common co-existent fracture. They adopted nonoperative as well as fixation of the clavicle for stabilization of the shoulder complex, and they noted stable shoulder function at the 6-month follow-up [2].

Badan et al found triple disruption of the complex needs to be managed by treating at least 2 structures for optimal healing and shoulder function. They mentioned that traumatic disruption of a single component is common and found to show excellent results irrespective of operative or non-operative method [3].

Edwards et al found in their study the importance of the intact clavicle and its stabilizing effect which when lost leads to the displacement of the scapular fragments due to the unopposed muscular forces on the scapula, thus considering all the floating shoulders to be unstable [8]. Poggetti et al recommend nonsurgical treatment in cases of intact SSSC and nonmedial displacement of the shoulder girdle less than 20 mm [7]. Ouede et al did a retrospective study on 11 subjects with SOCT. They recommended osteosynthesis of the ribs, which

makes it possible to restore the integrity and wall stability, it also quickly restores respiratory function and also reduces pain and duration of ventilation. They gave priority to the fixation of clavicular fractures, which allows the indirect reduction of the fracture of the scapula [8].

Our current report mentions the lateral shoulder impaction injury and its management. Though rare and difficult fracture to treat, a good clinical result can be obtained with meticulous planning.

Conclusions

All studies concerning this type of trauma resulting in floating, dropping or unstable shoulder girdle discuss the co-existent features like ribs fractures or pneumothorax as "associated lesions". If we consider the lateral impaction hypothesis as correct, the possible lesions are not "associated", but "co-existent". They occur as a result of the same mechanism and they should properly planned and proper protocols should be followed.

In the above presented case report, the surgery was meticulously planned, resulting in positive and successful outcome of the surgery as seen in 6 months follow up.

Additional Information

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